

Indian Agricultural Marketing being benefitted by using PPP: Special Perspective of Bihar State

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Abstract:-

A public-private partnership is a contractual treaty involving a public organization (local, state or federal) and a private sector body. It provides an opportunity for private sector participation in financing, designing, construction, operation and maintenance of public sector programmed and projects. Some of the benefits of public and private sector confluence are - PPP combines the unsurpassed features of the public and private sector collectively, reduced open public capital investment & mobilization of private capital. Central Government has taken some initiative as the reforms in PPP as far as agriculture is concerned, as: Institutional credit for agriculture sector, Agro Infrastructure Fund, Agricultural Mechanization etc. Government has recently taken some steps for increasing investment and growth in farming sector which comprise Micro Irrigation Fund for water use efficiency, creation of Long Term Irrigation Fund (LTIF), promotion of commercial organic farming, Public private partnership (PPP) model etc.

The Indian Government is operational on PPP mode in the farm sector to improve produces, reduce losses and enhance cultivator incomes. PPP initiatives will crowd in private capital in agriculture, leverage public investment and farmers in a shared vision of dynamic and value-added growth in the sector.

PPPs are needed that introduce India's farm sector to the state-of-the-art. Bihar government was the one of the earliest government to start PPPs. Bihar Government has taken many policy initiatives to create suitable investment climate for private sector.

Keywords: PPP, Central Government, Bihar Government, Planning Commission of India, GDP, MSP, APMC etc.

Introduction:-

A public private partnership is a cooperative and collaborative arrangement between two or more public and private sectors, typically of a long-term nature (Hodge and Grave, 2007). A public-private partnership is a contractual treaty involving a public organization (local, state or federal) and a private sector

body. Through this treaty, skills and assets of each sector (public and private) are mobilized in the transfer of a facility or service for the consumption of the general public. Over and above the sharing of the resources each party reveals risks and rewards likely in the delivery of the service and/or the facility. The PPP practices harness scarce public resources, create more competitive environment, and help drive efficiency and cost reduction. Planning Commission of India has described the PPP in a broad term as “a mode of instigating government programs/projects in partnership with the private sector. It provides an opportunity for private sector participation in financing, designing, construction, operation and maintenance of public sector programmed and projects. Risk allocation plays a imperative role in PPP management. Preplanned proposals with deadlines, finances, methods and materials will lead to expected outcome of Public Private Partnership (PPP), for which it is customary.

Literature Review:-

The underlying principle for public sector involvement differs between several kinds of services and influences the form of involvement required (Paul and Margaret, 2003). Agriculture is heavily weighted to GDP for high-value produce (animal husbandry, dairy, poultry, horticulture, and fish products); 75% of the value of Agriculture GDP today is contributed by these produce (Shukla et al., 2016). India's expenditure on irrigation R&D and education is currently about 0.6% of the GDP from agriculture and related activities which needs to be elevated at least to 1.0 per cent (Planning Commission 2011). It can be implemented in several areas like agricultural supply chain management, agricultural research, agricultural extension management, watershed management, Biotechnology, etc. (Rae et al., 2017). PPPs thus allow the public sector to influence more financial resources by managing the private sector as an intermediary (Anonymous, 2011).

Objective of the Study:

- To highlight the need of PPP in agriculture
- To recognize the benefits of PPP
- To highlight central government and Bihar government initiatives

Description: -

NEED FOR PPP IN AGRICULTURE SECTOR

Public Private Partnership (PPP) is most ideal in developing countries for successful delivery of infrastructure facilities like health care services, transportation and education as it is more effectual there. In developing countries, rural-urban immigration has increased urbanization at same time socio-economic improvements have increased the demand for infrastructure and also demands on maintaining and operating the existing infrastructure. Thus private sector could be involved through mutually beneficial agreement for resourceful use of resources, better project design and implementation,

availability of modern technology and improved operation combine to deliver efficiency.

BENEFITS OF PUBLIC PRIVATE PARTNERSHIP

Some of the benefits of public and private sector confluence are discussed below:

i.) **Respective strengths:** PPP combines the unsurpassed features of the public and private sector collectively. The private sector can leverage its returns in greater operational efficiency, creative financing, and more complex delivery systems, lower costs of distribution, faster decision-making, management flexibility and innovation. The public sector can provide strategic direction – the choice, location and pricing of infrastructure; ensure transparency in procurement and above all, through capital or user fee subsidies, or commitments to purchasing arrangements, enable private firms to go through large markets with guaranteed consumers.

ii) Reduced open public capital investment & mobilization of private capital

iii) Bundling design, construction and operations: Rather than there being separate design, construction, financing, operations and maintenance arrangements, as with traditional public sector procurement of infrastructure, involvement of the private sector encourages these functions to be pooled under one contractor.

iv) Cost savings: Efficiency can be higher in the private sector, with greater opportunities for economies of scale, strong project management skills, response risk management, more attuned skills, innovative technologies and lower overheads.

v) Expanding reach to unaffordable projects: PPP arrangements also allow the public sector to consider otherwise unaffordable projects.

vi) More efficient implementation: Adaptable subcontracting and procurement, quicker agreements for new capital financing, more effective decision-making and stronger project management are some of the uninterrupted benefits of private sector participation in PPP paradigms.

SOME EXAMPLES OF PPPs IN AGRICULTURAL VALUE CHAIN

i) PPP for produce diversification and contract farming: The Punjab state government encouraged Punjab Agro Food-grains Corporation (PAFC) had an assertive target of getting a fourth of its acreage under non-grains. To achieve the target, the Government has taken the cooperation of private partners through the contract farming route. The Punjab Government through PAFC refunded extension cost to CF facilitators/ agencies at the rate of Rs 150 per acre for three years to force contract farming with the goal of achieving diversification.

ii) Creating producer bodies through PPP: Another exceptional case of PPPs is the Mahagrapes was set up by the Maharashtra State Agricultural Marketing Board (MSAMB), the National Horticulture Board (NHB), the Department of Cooperation, and Government of Maharashtra, Agricultural Products Export Development Authority (APEDA), the National Cooperative Development

Corporation (NCDC), and is by the grape growers themselves for the benefit of grape growers. The objective was to encourage the marketing of grapes worldwide and to think about the problems of quality and rejection in the international market faced by the growers' yield.

iii) PPP for agricultural extension: In Madhya Pradesh (MP), there was a Public-Private Partnership (PPP) in agricultural extension connecting the Department of Agriculture (DoA), the national institute of agricultural extension management (MANAGE) based in Hyderabad, the Government of MP and the Dhenuka Aristech Group, which markets plant protection chemicals together with eco-friendly products. The partnership was intended to foster increased productivity on farms and improve the standards of living, of farmers, providing services, cyber dhobis (countryside/highway eateries in India serving local ethnic food), exhibitions and market linkages for agricultural produce (Singh, 2011).

iv) PPP for organic production: Kohinoor Food Ltd (KFL) established in Uttarakhand, a leading company of India in the systematic marketing of rice including Basmati rice made an attempt for a PPP in organic basmati rice. To increase its supply, KFL tried to find farmers for the organic programme and with the help of Uttarakhand Organic Commodity Board (UOCB), a state government agency, KFL approached Basmati farmers' association in Dehradun district.

v) PPP for marketing infrastructure: Terminal market is a PPP (public-private partnership) model that relates production center with the consumption center. The Government of India is looking to promote terminal markets in cities of Mumbai, Nashik, Nagpur, Chandigarh, Rae Patna, Bhopal and Kolkata as well as Ahmedabad and Surat in Gujarat. These markets will function on a hub-spoke format, wherein the hub (market) would be linked to different collection centers (spokes), which in turn would be situated at key production centers for ease of farmers.

vi) PPP for agricultural services: For improving the condition and promoting the tribal cultivators, the government of Gujarat & Deere and Company (Global Leader concerning agricultural equipment) are working jointly towards a Public Private Partnership (PPP) model, which is an example.

Initiatives taken by the Central Government as the reforms in Public Private Partnership in agriculture.

Agriculture being a concern of State, the State Government is principally responsible for the growth and promotion of agriculture sector and developing perspective policies for their respective States and guarantying effective implementation of the programs/schemes. On the other hand, Government of India supplements the powers of the State Governments through different Schemes/ Programs. The details of a variety of schemes, reforms and policies are given below.

- Unprecedented enhancement in budget allocation

- Fixing of MSP at one-and-a half times the production cost
- Increase in procurement from farmers
- Income support to farmers through PM KISAN
- Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana (PMFBY)
- Institutional credit for agriculture sector
- Providing Soil Health Cards to farmers
- Promotion of organic farming in the country
- Neem Coating of Urea
- Agri Infrastructure Fund
- Promotion of FPOs Scheme
- National Bee and Honey Mission (NBHM)
- Pradhan Mantri Krishi Sinchai Yojana (PMKSY)
- Micro Irrigation Fund
- Agricultural Mechanization
- Changes in Disaster Relief Standards
- Setting up of E-NAM extension Platform
- Improvement in agricultural produce logistics, Introduction of Kisan Rail
- Conception of a Start-up Eco system in farming and allied sector

Government has taken a number of steps for increasing investment in farming sector such as enhanced institutional credit to cultivators; promotion of scientific warehousing infrastructure for increasing shelf life of farm produce; conception of Agro-tech Infrastructure Fund for making agriculture competitive and profitable; increasing commercial organic farming etc. Government is implementing different schemes for supply of agricultural inputs, like seeds, fertilizers, agricultural equipments and machinery, irrigation facilities, institutional credit, etc., at subsidized rates to the cultivators in the country. Government has recently taken some steps for increasing investment and growth in farming sector which comprise Micro Irrigation Fund for water use efficiency, creation of Long Term Irrigation Fund (LTIF), promotion of commercial organic farming, Public private partnership (PPP) model etc.

The Indian Government is operational on PPP mode in the farm sector to improve produces, reduce losses and enhance cultivator incomes. PPP initiatives will crowd in private capital in agriculture, leverage public investment and farmers in a shared vision of dynamic and value-added growth in the sector. PPP mode will also increase the profit of farmers and improve their impact. The primary objective of this PPP scheme is to enhance the income of small scaled farmers by creating additional rate, - technology extension to market linkages, from provisioning of quality inputs, and value addition. PPP mode also expected to lead to modernizing agriculture practices, promoting research in climate resilient crops, developing agriculture and rural infrastructure, and increasing agricultural exports. PPP mode will assist the States to unbolt the full potential of their own agro-climatic regions, and wide

variety of agricultural-produce and help producers to incorporate better with domestic and export markets.

A major game changer for the farm segment can be the public private partnership model. PPPs, which form the collective power of all the stakeholders in the farming ecosystem—private companies, the government, and even education and research and development—can renovate the sector at multiple levels. With the government bestowing and co-financing the back-end of the value chain, the private sector and cultivator contributions doing the rest, the farm sector can still remain as a main engine of rural growth and poverty reduction in India.

The Indian government is working on following steps for effective use of PPP model in Agriculture.

1. Investing in smarter value chains

Indian government and private sector can work together for the development of the food-processing industry and the main profit of PPP Mode can be farm extension services, enhance price realization, outline intermediaries and perk up the supply chain through backward and forward linkages.

An important role of the government, in addition of funding by means of the PPP, will also be to create a facilitating environment for private investment. This needs to be done through duty exemptions, tax rationalization, priority sector lending, increase in public spending, and foreign direct investment (FDI). These are the steps that will catalyze private sector investments in supply chain infrastructure and services, conducting to a reduction in waste and greater value-addition.

2. Improving access to credit, technology and markets

PPPs are needed that introduce India's farm sector to the state-of-the-art. Information technology (IT) and biotechnology have the capability to transform farming, raising its production quantity and outputs. PPPs targeted at offering cultivators vital information, methodologies and new-age tech tools are the requirement of the day. Technology can bring to cultivators critical knowledge and regulation on matters related to weather patterns, crop rotation, going organic, fertilizer use—all at the click of a few keystrokes from the keyboard, or better still, a simple text message from their mobile phones.

Biotechnology, for now, can equip cultivators with techniques that help them grow high-yield crops, manage pests, better make use of waste water and focus on nutrition.

The valuable impact of technology has found likeness in the remarkable turnaround and innovations that have been made in the cereal production trade. This success can be replicated in critical areas, such as oil seeds and pulses, which are highly import-demanding, through PPPs. In the same way, PPP plans, targeted at helping cultivators connect with their bazaars and financial institutions for micro-funding, can lead in massive alterations in the rural economy.

3. Building farmer resilience to environmental shocks

India's farmers are threatened persistently by adverse weather and environmental conditions that curse disaster for their produce. Extreme conditions, such as flooding and droughts, continue to affect India's farming community, and PPPs immunizing the agricultural sector against the vagaries of nature can be a lifesaver. In fact, in a country where cultivator suicides are common, such involvements can save lives in reality. PPPs that help the farm sector deal with weather shocks, and enable cultivators to insulate themselves from risk insurance, etc., can emerge as an important adjunct.

PPP model in special reference of Bihar

Bihar government was the one of the earliest government to start PPPs. Most of the earliest initiatives of PPPs were either contracting in or contracting out in nature. Some of them were not likely to qualify as PPP when partnership rules are taken into consideration. The Government of Bihar repealed the APMC act with effect from 2006. In comparison to average size of long holding of the nation that is 1.57 hectare Bihar average land holding appears to be of 0.75 hectare. Contract Farming appears to be helpful in reducing the market and transaction costs so that small and poor farmers can obtain benefits. The contract farming is an area to be focused that will positively impact the incomes of cultivators of Bihar. Pepsi Corporation is likely to initiate contract farming in the state for the potato crop. Litchi, guava, banana and mango are the major fruits and tomato, cauliflower, onion, okra, brinjal and potato are the major vegetables of Bihar. The agriculture growth rate of Bihar is not uniform till now. The public investment ratio, in comparison with the other states of India, as a ratio of Bihar Agriculture GDP has been much lower. To have efficient functioning of market road infrastructure is much important. Poor rural roads restricts farmers to have access of markets, increases time and cost of transport. This causes the deterioration of crop quality. Telecommunication infrastructure also plays an important role in overall growth of economy. Bihar behind the other states was lagging the telecommunication infrastructure few years ago but due to interest of private sector in business it is bound to grow at a rapid pace.

Enhancement of private sector investment due to requirement of huge investment in Bihar for development of markets, post-harvest infrastructure and cool chain & processing units is pertinent. Bihar Government has taken many policy initiatives to create suitable investment climate for private sector.

Due to underdevelopment of industries including farming industry for decades and loss of confidence are the major factors influencing the proper implementation of PPP model in Bihar. In the last few years the state government has increased the development expenditure that will appear to be fruitful if the supplement of the investment under various central schemes comes together in business to remodellize the agricultural marketing infrastructure.

In Bihar under the scheme of Grameen Bhandaran Yojana, credit linked back-ended subsidy is being provided to create godowns in rural areas for scientific storage of processed farm produce, farm inputs, agricultural commodities etc. Apart from the projects in the sector of the Government of India, the Bihar government has implemented food processing policy in 2008 and established a separate directorate in the state. Food parks in Bhagalpur-Katihar and Muzzaffarpur-Vaishali regions have been approved by the government. The efforts are being made to revitalize closed units of sugar industries bringing up lease agreements with investors like HPCL and Reliance etc. industries.

Conclusion:

Bihar Government has taken many policy initiatives to create suitable investment climate for private sector. In shifting the employment structure to achieve more profitable marketing, processing and distribution sector, skill based vocational education program will be more helpful. Bihar is running skill based education program currently and central skill based education program is also being executed here in Bihar.

Much more things and practices are being implemented by the Bihar Government to enhance the agricultural income under PPP model to overcome the demerits of traditional agricultural policies.

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